

Action Plan

Towards FAIR
Implementation
in the Dutch
Social Sciences
and Humanities

April 2026

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Introduction

A collaborative Action Plan

Over the past years, many research infrastructures, research performing organisations (RPOs), and funders have expressed their commitment to the FAIR principles. - i.e., ensuring that digital research objects (such as data, software, training materials) are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Yet, **implementing the FAIR principles remains a significant challenge across the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in the Netherlands**, leaving a gap between the ambitions as outlined in policies and guidelines, and actual practices. This is due to a combination of technical/infrastructural constraints (for example, unavailability of semantic resources for meaningful data annotation for interoperability) and organisational aspects (such as insufficient recognition for time investment into making data FAIR, lack of a clear organisational structure that sustains FAIR data generation).

The Action Plan towards FAIR Implementation in the SSH addresses these challenges with a focus on the practical realities. Its purpose is twofold: first, to provide a clear overview of the key bottlenecks that stand in the way of effective FAIR implementation. Second, to propose concrete and actionable steps that stakeholders can take to move forward and reduce the gap between FAIR ambitions and practices. While many reports and roadmaps already exist, this Action Plan is unique in its **focus on the practical realities of those working with RDM and FAIR in the SSH**: the data stewards, repository managers, infrastructure providers, researchers, and policy officers who navigate the FAIR data principles in their daily work.

There are manifold benefits stemming from FAIRification of digital objects:

Cost reduction and Sustainability

Reusable materials means less time and resources used to collect data unnecessarily. This translates to less data storage and processing costs. Moreover, for research which collects data from, or co-produces data together with, specific individuals or communities, making these data more FAIR reduces the risk of 'over-researching' certain populations.

Science and Innovation

FAIR enables integration of different data/digital objects, and therefore unlocks new and faster research opportunities for multiple domains and for cross-disciplinary research as well as for collaboration with public and private partners.

Informed citizens

In cases where data collection involves personal or sensitive data, incorporating elements of FAIRness into the consent process (where relevant) facilitates dialogue with data subjects about the conditions underwhich they are amenable to their personal data being shared and reused.

Societal impact

FAIR means rich and persistent documentation that allows research institutions to measure the impact of research, fostering transparency and trust in science.

FAIR Implementation Action Plan

The Social Sciences and Humanities in the Netherlands

Bottleneck

Recommendations

Action

1. FAIR roles and responsibilities are unclear and uneven across institutions, leading to misalignment, gaps, and resistance - especially in small organisations

- Design a blueprint of RDM roles & tasks
- Establish participatory and transparent governance framework for RDM

Map

Untangle FAIR roles and processes

2. Disconnected RDM systems and DMPs treated as paperwork leave researchers unequipped and create repeated effort, inconsistencies, and risks to data quality

- Revise DMPs process
- Build more robust FAIR-enabling digital environments

Equip

Enable FAIR-by-design RDM at RPOs

3. Researchers and managers see little incentive to invest in FAIR, as data and software outputs receive minimal recognition compared to publications

- Integrate FAIR into institutional leadership priorities
- Value FAIR contributions as research outputs

Reward

Make FAIR Count

4. FAIR skills remain uneven across roles, with misconceptions, privacy concerns, and fragmented training preventing effective and confident implementation

- Create FAIR and RDM module for Bachelor and Master's courses
- Organise bring-your-own-(meta)data events

Train

Make FAIR tangible to (future) data providers

5. Professionals struggle to keep up with evolving FAIR practices due to siloed communication, scarce capacity, and limited SSH-specific exchange

- Build shared expert capacity for smaller and resource-limited institutes
- Create SSH FAIR Ambassadors program

Share

Foster knowledge exchange on FAIR

MAP

Untangle FAIR roles and processes

Bottleneck: Within Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), responsibilities for FAIR and research data management are often unclear and unevenly distributed. Different institutional structures—across and within universities, faculties, and research institutes—mean that roles, mandates, and reporting lines vary widely. This makes coordination difficult and leads to duplication, gaps in responsibility and competition instead of open collaboration. Misalignment between central units, faculties, and research groups further fragments expertise, while collaboration across IT, data management, and research perspectives is hindered by differing terminology, planning cycles, and organisational cultures. Many key contributors to FAIR implementation lack formal recognition within projects. In addition, differences in institutional size and administrative capacity mean that small institutes face structural obstacles in hiring specialised staff or procuring FAIR-enabling systems, making national-level support and coordination essential. Moreover, existing FAIR approaches remain largely modelled on STEM disciplines, with insufficient adaptation to qualitative and interpretive disciplines, which may create resistance against FAIR policies.

Recommendation #1

Design a blueprint of RDM roles & tasks

Objective

Improve understanding of different organisational structures, highlighting strengths and weaknesses, and provide clear guidance on how to improve effectiveness and efficiency of Local Digital Competence Centers (L-DCCs) efficiently across organisations. This knowledge would also help smaller institutes covering the main roles and tasks.

Suggested actions

For DCC-Implementation Network:

- **Map roles.** Capture current picture of who is responsible for what when it comes to RDM and FAIR Implementation at different organisations using existing tools (e.g., FAIR-Impact Instruments), but also giving professional support staff the assignment to describe their tasks. Use this action to identify double work, overlaps, gaps. Work on this has been initiated within this project and others, such as [SLIPPRS-NL](#), but it should be continued.

For DCC-Implementation Network and Landelijk Beraad Digitale Infrastructuur (LBDI):

- **Prepare blueprint for roles.** Design a blueprint chart that specifies what roles ought to exist, at what level and what their responsibilities have to be, depending on the size of a particular institution. The framework should address: (a) Functions/roles: for instance, data stewards, privacy officer, information managers; ,... (b) Responsibility: i.e. compliance, facilitation, expertise, ownership; (c) Organizational level: Operational, managerial, strategic.

Expected outcome

The RDM roles' blueprint would help to configure DCCs in a way that is interoperable across institutions, facilitating cross-organisation exchange. Moreover, it would foster synergies and ensure sustainable growth paths for RDM roles. It would also help achieving more clarity on the different processes involved in RDM, and the complex interplay among them.

Recommendation #2

Establish participatory and transparent governance framework for RDM

Objective

Creating inclusive, transparent, and discipline-sensitive governance structures for RDM and FAIR implementation within RPOs' governance should ensure that decisions about policies, infrastructures, and priorities are made collaboratively—bringing together researchers, data stewards, IT, legal, and policy experts from different disciplines/methods.

Suggested actions

For data/software policy officers and management at RPOs:

- **Build participatory and transparent decision-making processes.** Design governance structures that include all relevant stakeholders in the formulation of RDM and FAIR policies, and ensure representation from different research subdisciplines, including qualitative and mixed-methods communities. Allow room for concepts such as reflexivity and positionality, and CARE principles, which can also be used to make data more Reusable. Improve transparency by, for example, publishing policy development procedures, committees' composition, and guiding criteria.
- **Empower FAIR and RDM experts with formal mandates.** Provide data stewards, information managers, and other RDM professionals with clear mandates to participate in institutional decision-making processes. Recognise these contributions as essential to institutional Open Science strategies and embed them in official governance documentation and reporting lines.

For DCC Coordinators:

- **Create cross-functional project teams** around specific flagship projects within organisations (and potentially between organisations), to use as testbeds for multi-role collaboration (including IT, data stewards, privacy officers) instead of asking researchers to go to each role individually.
- Once FAIR Implementation projects are concluded, organise **debriefing sessions** discussing FAIR implementation cases that are seen from the different perspectives (IT, RDM, research, privacy), so that everybody can give input from their own perspective, and then see it from the others' perspectives. This nurtures mutual understanding in future projects.
- Data governance and strategy decisions can be facilitated by ensuring that various SSH disciplines are represented in inter-faculty **Research Data Governance Board** with relevant competence and mandate to enable FAIR data services.

Expected outcome

RPOs will have governance systems where FAIR and RDM policies are developed through transparent, participatory, and discipline-aware processes, focusing on the participation of SSH researchers to ensure that FAIR implementation will be more attractive and achievable for subdisciplines of SSH that are not quantitative. Moreover, the mandates and tasks of central and faculty data stewards are clarified and organised in a collaborative manner with regards to policy development, process improvement, trainings or hands on-support. Involving RDM professionals in decision-making processes is expected to foster policy implementation; also, collaboration across research support roles make workflows for researchers run more smoothly.

EQUIP

Enable FAIR-by-design RDM at RPOs

Bottleneck: At various stages in the research cycle (planning, collecting, analysing, publishing), researchers need to be equipped properly to meet data management demands. While the Data Management Plan has been introduced to keep researchers focused on these demands, in practice it is experienced as an administrative hurdle which, once overcome, is quickly forgotten. Moreover, there is little integration between systems servicing the various stages of the research cycle (project administration, data management, reference managers, data repositories). This may compel the professionals involved to do redundant work, awkwardly transferring data between systems and entering metadata repeatedly, with the risk of inconsistency and even loss of data. The following recommendations outline some of the steps which can be taken to remedy these obstacles, thus improving the quality and sustainability of data as a type of knowledge output which has value in its own right.

Recommendation #3 **Revise DMPs process**

Objective

Transform Data Management Plans (DMPs) from compliance checklists into living, connected instruments that guide FAIR implementation throughout the research lifecycle.

Suggested actions

For local DCCs / Research Data Management offices:

- **Simplify and tailor DMP templates** to disciplinary needs, if possible with optional extensions

to generic templates, focusing on practical decisions about metadata, storage, and reuse, instead of abstract requirements. Concrete examples would be DMP-questions about data collection and sampling (for statistical methodologies), bias and positionality statements (for heritage studies), and data granularity and hierarchy (for linguistics). Be mindful of not having too many highly-specific templates, but look for commonalities and synergies.

- **Introduce reminders or checkpoints** to revise DMPs at key project milestones (e.g. publication, data collection, project closure) rather than treating them as static documents.
- In interaction with funders, **strengthen collaboration** between RPOs and funders to harmonise DMP expectations and allow automatic export of information for compliance reporting.

For local IT-departments in interaction with a national infrastructural partner (e.g, SURF):

- **Link DMPs to other institutional systems** (e.g. ethics review, DPIA, storage, archiving, and repositories) so that information (metadata) entered once can be reused across workflows and updated automatically. For this, proper machine-readable formats and/or machine-Actionable DMP solutions should be adopted and interconnected with other systems, in alignment with international initiatives such as [OSTrails](#).

Expected outcome

Data Management Plans become active components of FAIR workflows, ensuring that metadata, documentation, and data-handling choices are consistent and reusable across systems. Researchers experience DMPs as supportive planning and reflection tools rather than administrative hurdles, while institutions gain better oversight of FAIR compliance and data quality.

Recommendation #4 **Build more robust FAIR-enabling digital environments**

Objective

Ensure that the IT infrastructure available to researchers is more FAIR-enabling, by ensuring access to integrated rather than isolated tools for researchers and addressing inequities for smaller institutes.

Suggested actions

For infrastructure providers:

- Providers of (components of) research infrastructure need to **deliver systems that are robust and interoperable** enough (production-ready, scalable), before RPOs are willing to invest in the implementation within their organization. Yet, in order to get there, it is likely that RPOs need to be involved in pilots and PoCs, with clear timelines, roles, and expectations.

For local IT departments:

- **RDM experts should be engaged early** in institutional decisions about infrastructure procurement (see Rec#2).
- When choosing (components of) technical infrastructure, **make decisions that are consistent with the values organisations subscribe to** (e.g. The Barcelona declaration, DORA).
- The organizational units responsible for maintaining the systems, should **follow training in open source and communitydriven development**.

For national network organisation (TDCC-SSH, SURF, DCC-Implementation Network):

- Address inequity in access to FAIR-enabling tools by (helping with) **negotiating pricing models** that are appropriate for smaller institutes and cultural heritage organisations. SURF and national infrastructures should play a brokerage role in securing affordable licenses and shared procurement models.
- Coordinate pilots and share best practices to avoid redundant investments and accelerate adoption of interoperable solutions (see Rec#9).

Expected outcome

Researchers and support staff work within cohesive, FAIR-enabling digital environments that reduce duplication and manual work. RPOs gain systems that are robust, scalable, and interoperable, enabling smoother FAIR implementation, avoid vendor lock-in and ensure long-term sustainability and transparency. Addressing licensing and procurement barriers ensures that FAIR-enabling systems become accessible to all RPOs, including small research institutes and heritage organisations.

REWARD

Make FAIR count

Bottleneck: Despite widespread high-level agreement on the value of FAIR, most researchers often see little personal incentive to invest time and resources in making their data or materials FAIR and, in parallel, the real value of FAIR is not fully visible for management. The effort required from researchers —especially for sensitive or complex data—can seem disproportionate to the rewards, as FAIR outputs rarely count in performance reviews, funding evaluations, or promotion criteria. Recognition is still primarily tied to traditional publications, while data and software remain undervalued research outputs. As a result, FAIR work is often driven by external mandates (for example, funding agencies requesting DMPs, journals requiring Open Access or Data Availability Statements).

Recommendation #5

Integrate FAIR into institutional leadership priorities

Objective

Encourage university and departmental management to recognise and reward FAIR data practices as a marker of research quality, transparency, and competitiveness.

Suggested actions

For University and Department managers:

- **Align with broader strategic goals:** Frame FAIR as contributing to innovation and transparency, values already prioritised in most institutional missions and aligning with funder and journal requirements.
- **Establish visibility and accountability:** Require regular reporting from departments on the proportion of publications accompanied by FAIR data or software. Showcase successful FAIR

contributions within institutional communications or host FAIR-awards to build prestige and visibility.

- **Leverage competitiveness and compliance:** Introduce benchmarking within and across academic institutions to highlight leaders in FAIR implementation, aligning with funder and journal requirements that increasingly support FAIR principles.
- **Reward FAIR contributions:** Include data and software publications in institutional performance evaluations, research assessments, and promotion criteria, in line with the [recommendations](#) of Öztürk et al. (2024) and (inter)national initiatives such as the [Recognition and Rewards](#) programme and [GraspOS](#).
- **Align with other research performing organisation:** Common recognition of FAIR efforts, aligned and transferable across institutions, would help researchers' portfolios to be recognized throughout their career.

Expected outcome

By embedding FAIR into leadership priorities and institutional reward structures, management becomes an ally in the efforts towards FAIR implementation, promoting both organisational alignment and long-term sustainability. This positions institutions that promote FAIR practices as leaders in data management, and helps attract top talent by enhancing institutions better standing in research.

Recommendation #6 Value FAIR contributions as research outputs

Objective

Encourage a cultural and structural shift within scientific merit evaluation systems at universities and funding bodies to treat FAIR materials (such as data, software, training documentation) as valued contributions by researchers to research quality and innovation, on par with traditional publications - especially considering that preparing sensitive SSH datasets for sharing may take a lot of additional time of researchers. Similar proposals are also made in the life sciences, see e.g. the [Elixir's policy brief](#) by Quaglia et al. (2025).

Suggested actions

For researchers:

- **Accelerate research progress:** Reuse available datasets or combine projects to speed up

the research outputs and reduce duplication of effort (shared materials, shared datasets). Reuse also makes researchers more aware of the benefits of FAIR.

- **Unlock new insights and innovation:** Pool datasets where possible to achieve larger sample and effect sizes, enabling research questions that would otherwise be unanswerable and thus contributing to new discoveries and to promote data reuse among other researchers.
- **Establish community-driven FAIR assessment criteria** and acceptability thresholds, conceptually similar to how traditional publications rely on peer-review. Complement quantitative indicators with qualitative assessments (such as presence of a descriptive README file, completeness of metadata).

For supervisors and PhD committees:

- **Acknowledge data and software publication as necessary deliverables and chapters** in PhD trajectories. Encourage PhD candidates to include FAIR data, software, protocols or other research outputs in their dissertations, and to make them citable by sharing them on a repository.

For journals and publishers:

- Journals should not accept “available upon request” as a sufficient demonstration of FAIR implementation.
- A FAIR checklist (such as the [FAIRaware](#) one) can be implemented at submission, seeing how the data statements matches each principle.

For funders:

- **Recognise previous FAIR contributions**, such as published datasets, created and maintained software, or reuse of existing data as a positive criterion in grant evaluations, and educate reviewers to apply these criteria in their evaluations.
- **Reward data reuse** and data pooling projects and discourage unnecessary duplication of data collection.

Expected outcome

When FAIR contributions are valued in evaluations, funding decisions, and publication practices, researchers gain clear incentives to invest in data stewardship and openness. This recognition will normalise FAIR as part of research excellence, reduce redundant data collection, and foster a culture where collaboration, reuse, and transparency are rewarded across the SSH. More funding can be distributed to studies relying on secondary data rather than new data collection - this way contributing to a bigger societal impact.

TRAIN

Make FAIR concrete for (future) data providers

Bottleneck: Researchers, support staff, and compliance officers across institutes lack sufficient knowledge to implement the FAIR principles in practice. Training opportunities are available yet fragmented, and FAIR is often perceived as overly technical or irrelevant by researchers — especially in qualitative disciplines. Misconceptions persist (“if my data cannot be open, it cannot be FAIR”), leading to hesitation or incomplete implementation. The SSH domain is distinctive in its frequent use of personal data, which raises significant challenges regarding de-identification. Qualitative researchers express uncertainty about how to make fieldnotes, interview transcripts, or ethnographic observations FAIR when data cannot be shared openly. Others question whether metadata alone is useful for discovery. Privacy officers and legal departments, meanwhile, often prioritise compliance over FAIR enablement, inadvertently creating barriers to sharing. Without a coherent training strategy and focused attention on metadata, especially when data cannot be shared, researchers miss opportunities to integrate FAIR thinking early and effectively in the research lifecycle.

Recommendation #7

Create FAIR and RDM module for Bachelor and Master’s courses

Objective

Equip future scientists and practioners with FAIR and Data Management skills starting early. Make it part of the research skills training, next to writing literature reviews and data analysis.

Suggested actions

Data stewards/RDM experts at SSH RPOs (coordinated by TDCC-SSH):

- **Create training materials targeting SSH Bachelor and (Research) Master students** that can be reused by lecturers from all Dutch universities. Materials should reflect diversity in the types of data and methods used in the SSH. Examples are: create training module for undergraduate courses based on the RDM Guidebook for students (Li et al, 2025) or the [CESSDA DMEG](#), make a specific training module for qualitative data, address data de-identification and privacy concerns and metadata-only models.

Lecturers:

- Include RDM elements in assignments to make it tangible for students, for instance: require (simplified) DMPs and/or data availability statements for theses or data assignments.

Expected outcome

Students become aware of RDM and FAIR and can take the knowledge with them in their future careers. Even if they don't pursue an academic career, they are more aware of academic RDM standards and can promote data sharing for research purposes among their employers.

Recommendation #8 **Organise bring-your-own-(meta)data events**

Objective

These events aim to show how researchers can document, and re-use existing data to create new and valuable research outcomes. By working with real examples, participants will learn practical ways to improve metadata quality and prepare data following FAIR principles.

Suggested actions

Data stewards/RDM experts at SSH RPOs:

- **Organize Metadata & FAIR Data workshops** during domain-specific academic conferences or other events to connect RDM to substantive research.
- **Provide hands-on guidance** on assessing, improving, and standardizing metadata for

existing datasets; facilitate exercises on data discovery without requiring new data collection. For instance, participants will work in small groups to review existing datasets, identify gaps or inconsistencies in metadata, standardize variable descriptions, assess reusability of datasets for their research, or annotate datasets using FAIR-compliant standards.

- These events should **include practical examples** such as improving metadata for interview studies, documenting variable definitions across multiple small surveys, or describing the workflow of an ethnographic project to support reuse without sharing raw data (for instance by exploring options to document or even deposit reflexive notes).

Expected outcome

These workshops accelerate the practical application of FAIR principles by providing hands-on experience. By working within their own research domains, participants will better appreciate the direct benefits of well-documented datasets to enhance the impact of their research, better assess research transparency (i.e., how did a study come to a certain conclusion) and demonstrate the value of FAIR data practices.

SHARE

Foster knowledge exchange on FAIR

Bottleneck: FAIR and RDM practices are constantly evolving, with new standards, tools, and requirements emerging at a rapid pace. For professionals working in research support, IT, or data stewardship, it is difficult to stay up to date. Communication between specialists in different domains—research, data management, IT, legal—remains fragmented, and cross-role collaboration often depends on personal networks rather than structured exchange. Smaller institutes face additional challenges: key roles such as data steward, information manager, or privacy officer are sometimes missing, blended, or only partially filled, leaving limited capacity to engage with developments or implement new practices. While national networks exist, they often address RDM in general terms, leaving little space for SSH-specific discussion.

Recommendation #9

Build shared expert capacity for smaller and resource-limited institutes

Objective

Enable smaller or less-resourced RPOs to access the specialised expertise needed for FAIR implementation through shared capacity and collaborative support structures.

Suggested actions

National infrastructures (ODISSEI, CLARIAH, TDCC-SSH, SURF, DANS, LCRDM, etc):

- **Develop a national or regional pool of FAIR and RDM experts** (e.g. data stewards, information managers, technical consultants) that institutions can call upon for short-term, high-priority projects such as repository setup, data audits, or FAIR assessments. There

are some examples in this direction (see FAIR Expertise Hub for the social sciences, SURF Consultancy, LCRDM Pool of experts, TDCC-SSH interoperability mission).

- **Document and publicly share examples** of successful collaboration models for cross-institutional RDM support.

Organisations management:

- **Reduce administrative barriers** for cross-institutional appointments by developing streamlined procedures and template agreements for temporary secondments, consultancy arrangements, or in-kind staff exchanges across RPOs. This is particularly important for small institutes that rely on shared expertise rather than full-time local staff.
- **Encourage in-kind support** for ad-hoc/short-term collaborations between institutes.
- **Encourage consortia or joint service models** such as the DCC-PO between smaller RPOs to share staff and resources for RDM tasks that cannot be sustained locally.

Expected outcome

Smaller institutes get access to state-of-the-art, specialistic knowledge on RDM to implement processes/systems in their own organisation and improve FAIR implementation, reducing inequality in capacity across the research landscape. Shared staffing models improve efficiency, ensure continuity of knowledge, and strengthen the overall resilience of the SSH RDM community.

Recommendation #10 **Create SSH FAIR Ambassadors program**

Objective

Create a network of researchers and data supporters who carried out flagship FAIR implementation projects to showcase real use cases/practices to other researchers and RDM practitioners, in alignment with existing networks and initiatives (such as the Data Stewardship Interest Group - DSIG and Open Science Communities) but reaching out to a broader audience less accustomed to discussing RDM topics.

Suggested actions

National infrastructures (ODISSEI, CLARIAH, TDCC-SSH, SURF, DANS, LCRDM, etc)

- **Localize who are the authorities** in a certain research area when it comes to FAIR implementation and organise SSH FAIR Ambassadors program.
- **Organise SSH FAIR Ambassadors roadshow presentations** at department units. Make as concrete as possible, ranging from “bare minimum” FAIR to FAIR-er: show trajectories.
- Organise SSH FAIR Ambassadors **roadshow presentations for privacy officers**. Highlight the societal impacts of FAIR data.
- **Ambassadors should highlight SSH-specific cases**, such as how metadata-only publication supports discovery of sensitive oral history materials, or how pooling multiple interview studies enabled a comparative analysis across regions.
- **Reward Ambassadors**: they should be either compensated for their time or anyway receive indirect benefits from participating in the programme.
- **Create the SSH-FAIR Compass**: a map of stakeholders, experts and initiatives in the field of FAIR Implementation for the SSH and a recommender system to help RDM professionals navigate the landscape depending on their specific need/question.

Expected outcome

Researchers and RDM professionals will learn about FAIR implementation from peers and by addressing real challenges that others have encountered and addressed, making FAIR implementation more concrete and tangible. Sharing best practices alongside failure stories is a powerful tool to address misconceptions around FAIR. Privacy officers will also gain more knowledge about FAIR implementation and facilitate it more. As the main point of contact for data openness concerns, they will have the opportunity to address questions and challenges raised by the researchers related to (meta)data privacy.

Closing words

A collaborative Action Plan

The Action Plan is the result of a collaborative and participatory process. In the course of the project Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH, financed by the Thematic Digital Competence Center (TDCC-SSH), two mapping exercises were conducted. The first one focused on technical implementation of FAIR, and used FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) to gather structured information on technologies and resources used in the DANS Data Station SSH, a platform which is crucial for enabling FAIR data in the SSH, enriched with observations gathered in interactions with SSH research projects. The second investigated organisational structures and decision-making processes at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) through a survey and semi-structured interviews. These mappings provided a first overview of where implementation succeeds and where barriers remain, and their insights are blended into the Action Plan.

Next to these mapping exercises, a Community Writing Sprint took place in September 2025. During this event, RDM professionals, infrastructure representatives, researchers, and policy makers came together to discuss the bottlenecks they experience, and co-create recommendations to overcome them. The writing sprint placed participants in the driver's seat: they shared experiences, shaped strategy and drove changes by co-writing parts of the Action Plan. This participatory approach ensured that the resulting Action Plan reflects the voices and expertise of those most directly involved in FAIR implementation. The list of authors and contributors is included in Appendix A.

Relation to existing initiatives

This Action Plan is not a stand-alone vision but is intended to complement and deepen existing strategic documents such as the TDCC-SSH Roadmap and the SSH Sector Plan. Where the Roadmap sets out broad ambitions and identifies activity clusters for the SSH domain, and the Sector Plan outlines investments in research capacity, the present Action Plan focuses on concrete steps to make FAIR work in practice and aims to provide a bridge between strategic aspirations and the daily realities of implementation. This is done while taking into consideration the specific features of the SSH over other domains, such as the abundance of sensitive and/or personal data which cannot be simply made openly available, and the fragmentation of data

providers including individual researchers who run small-scale studies with limited RDM curation capacity and/or smaller cultural heritage institutions with limited access to RDM tools and technologies.

The recommendations included in this Action Plan are meant to **inform and complement** initiatives for FAIRification and Data infrastructures so that future activities are targeted to solve concrete bottlenecks for FAIR Implementation. NWO funding remains a fundamental instrument to ensure FAIRification of digital objects in Dutch RPOs by improving access to skills, tools, resources, and capacity.

While the Action Plan is produced by and for the Dutch SSH research community, the contributors (listed in **Appendix A**) acknowledge that some of the recommendations will only work in conjunction with global developments, and hope that international communities, such as the Research Data Alliance Working Groups, engage with the content of this document and build on the experiences of the Dutch FAIR Implementation landscape. Conversely, there may be recommendations which are not SSH-specific in their substance, but may benefit from more acknowledgement and effort specifically within the SSH-domain.

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Appendix A:

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Ronald Siebes	VU Amsterdam	0000-0001-8772-7904	✓		
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Action Plan

Towards FAIR
Implementation
in the Dutch
Social Sciences
and Humanities

